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The REX model documentation

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The REX renewable energy expansion model

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Abstract

To achieve the ambitious goals of keeping the global temperature rise well below 2 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5 degrees Celsius set by the Paris Agreement, the electricity system is undergoing so-far unseen drastic changes. The share of fluctuating low CO₂ emitting technologies such as wind and solar photovoltaics is increasing rapidly in the electricity system, which brings more challenges in grid operation and load balance due to the intermittency of variable renewable energy resources. Many actors envision a future renewable electric power system dominated by wind and solar. For example, a system dominated by solar and wind will face challenges to cover the electricity demand at nights without wind. The variability of wind and solar may be handled by transmission, storage, demand side management, fuel production (like hydrogen) or flexibilities from other sectors (heat, industry, transport). Therefore, it is important to understand how a renewable electricity system would be optimally designed and the requirement of different variation management strategies in such a system. In the face of these transitions, we develop a state-of-the-art techno-economic cost optimization model with high temporal and spatial resolution for the capacity investment and dispatch of wind, solar, hydro, biofuel, natural gas power generation, transmission and storage, as well as demand side resources. The future electricity demand is satisfied under the constraints of low CO₂ emission and resource endowments. The REX model has been implemented in Julia language and the formulation is described in this document.

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1. Introduction

REX stands for “Renewable Energy eXpansion”.

REX is an open source and open data modelling toolbox developed by Xiaoming Kan under the supervision of Fredrik Hedenus and Lina Reichenberg at Chalmers University of Technology. REX can be adopted as a useful tool in techno-economic cost optimization of the future electricity system investment in capacity expansion and dispatch of generation, transmission, storage, demand-side resources. The model components and structure are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. REX model components and structure.

REX includes:

- Dispatchable generators, such as natural gas, biomass CHP, biogas power plants
- Generators with time-varying power availability, such as wind and solar generators
- Hydroelectricity with inflow and spillage
- Transmission grids with losses
- Storage units with efficiency losses
- Demand-side resources

2. Notation

2.1 Model Indices and Sets

R	Regions
T	Time steps
X	Thermal technologies
Y	VRE technologies
S	Storage technologies
M	Demand-side resources
M	Demand-side resources

2.2 Parameters

D_{rt}	Demand in time-step t in region r [MWh]
C_n	Annualized investment cost for generation technology n [$\frac{\$}{MW}$]
C_r	Annualized investment cost for storage [$\frac{\$}{MWh}$]
$C_{rr'}$	Annualized investment cost for transmission line rr' [$\frac{\$}{MW}$]
R_n	Variable cost for generation technology and demand-side resource [$\frac{\$}{MWh}$]
A_{nr}	Area available for VRE resource n in region r [km^2]
ρ_{nr}	Capacity density assigned to VRE resource n in region r [$\frac{MW}{km^2}$]
$\eta_{n,\gamma,s}$	Efficiency for generation technology, transmission and storage
O_{nrt}	Output of variable quantity for VRE technology n in region r in time-step t
W_{rmax}	Maximum storage level of hydro reservoir in region r [MWh]
W_{rmin}	Minimum storage level of hydro reservoir in region r [MWh]
f_{irt}	Hydro inflow to reservoirs in region r during time-step t [MWh]
f_{irt}'	Hydro inflow to RoRs in region r during time-step t [MWh]
H_r'	Hydro RoR generation capacity in region r [MW]
H_r	Hydro reservoir generation capacity in region r [MW]

φ_n Fraction of demand-response that belongs to segment n

E_n Emission factor of generation technology n [$\frac{gCO_2}{MWh}$]

Cap Carbon cap

2.3 Decision Variables

x_{nr} Capacity of thermal technology n in region r [MW]

y_{nr} Capacity of VRE technology n in region r [MW]

$z_{rr'}$ Capacity of transmission between region r and r' [MW]

u_r Storage in region r [MWh]

α_{nrt} Generation using thermal technology n in region r during time-step t [MWh]

β_{nrt} Generation using VRE technology n in region r during time-step t [MWh]

$\gamma_{rr't}$ Exported electricity from region r to r' during time-step t [MWh]

$\gamma_{r'rt}$ Imported electricity from region r' to r during time-step t [MWh]

θ_{rt} Storage level in region r during time-step t [MWh]

δ_{rt} Electricity into storage in region r during time-step t [MWh]

ε_{rt} Electricity out of storage in region r during time-step t [MWh]

w_{rt} Hydro reservoir storage level in region r during time-step t [MWh]

f_{ort} Hydro outflow from reservoirs in region r during time-step t [MWh]

f_{ort}' Hydro outflow through the turbine in region r during time-step t [MWh]

f_{ort}'' Hydro outflow bypassing turbine in region r during time-step t [MWh]

h_{rt} Hydro generation in region r during time-step t [MWh]

h_{rt}' Hydro RoR generation in region r during time-step t [MWh]

λ_{rt} KKT multiplier of the demand constraint in region r during time-step t [$\frac{\$}{MWh}$]

v_{nrt} Curtailed demand of segment n in region r during time-step t [MWh]

C_r Annual net electricity system cost for country (or region) r [$\$$]

C_r^{av} Nodal net average system cost for country (or region) r [$\frac{\$}{MWh}$]

3. Model Formulation

In this study, a future interconnected European electricity system is modelled during one year with hourly time resolution. The annual electricity system cost is minimized under the constraints of meeting demand, resource endowments, and a CO₂ cap.

3.1 Objective Function

Minimize total annual system cost: thermal power capacity and generation costs + VRE capacity costs + storage cost + transmission capacity cost + demand-response cost. Therefore, the objective function is formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min} \quad & \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{n \in X} (C_n x_{nr} + R_n \alpha_{nrt}) + \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{n \in Y} (C_n y_{nr}) + \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{n \in S} (C_s u_r) + \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{r' \in R} (0.5 C_{rr'} z_{rr'}) \\ & + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{n \in M} (R_n v_{nrt}). \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

3.2 Demand Balance Requirements

The electricity demand has to be satisfied through generation, trade, storage and demand-response to guarantee the security of the electricity supply.

$$\sum_{n \in X} \alpha_{nrt} + \sum_{n \in Y} \beta_{nrt} + \sum_{n \in M} \varepsilon_{nrt} + \sum_{r' \in R} (\eta_Y \gamma_{r't} - \gamma_{rr't}) + \sum_{n \in S} (\eta_S \varepsilon_{rt} - \delta_{rt}) + h_{rt} \geq D_{rt} \leftrightarrow \lambda_{rt}, \quad (2)$$

where λ_{rt} is the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) multiplier associated with the constraint. The KKT multiplier indicates the marginal price of supplying additional demand at node r in hour t [1].

3.3 CO₂ Emissions Limits

The total CO₂ emission is constrained by the carbon cap:

$$\sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{n \in X} (E_n \frac{\alpha_{nrt}}{\eta_n}) \leq \text{Cap} \quad (3)$$

3.4 Thermal Energy

Thermal generation is upper-bounded by capacity:

$$0 \leq \alpha_{nrt} \leq x_{nr} \quad (4)$$

3.5 Variable Renewable Energy

The investment in VRE capacity is limited by the upper limit, which is constrained by area considerations and the maximum capacity density:

$$0 \leq y_{nr} \leq y_{nr}^{\max} = \rho_{nr} A_{nr} \quad (5)$$

VRE generation is upper-bounded by momentary weather conditions and capacity:

$$0 \leq \beta_{nrt} \leq O_{nrt} \gamma_{nr} \quad (6)$$

3.6 Hydro Energy

For hydro reservoir, due to environmental concern, the water in the reservoir cannot exceed the maximum storage level W_{rmax} . In addition, the water in the reservoir is required to be above the minimum level. Therefore, the storage level has a lower bound W_{rmin} .

$$W_{rmin} \leq w_{rt} \leq W_{rmax}. \quad (7)$$

The reservoir storage level is also affected by the inflow and outflow,

$$w_{r,t+1} = w_{rt} + f_{irt} - f_{ort}, \quad (8)$$

where the constraint is circular so that the storage level in the last time-step of the year equals the storage level in the first time-step of the year.

Part of the outflow f_{ort}'' bypasses the turbine to balance the ecosystem and human needs for water downstream. The outflow f_{ort} has to satisfy the minimum environmental flow requirement Q^{min} [2, 3]. The flow f_{ort}' through the turbine is upper-bounded by the hydro reservoir capacity H_r .

$$f_{ort} = f_{ort}' + f_{ort}'', \quad (9)$$

$$f_{ort} \geq Q^{min}, \quad (10)$$

$$0 \leq f_{ort}' \leq H_r. \quad (11)$$

For hydro RoR, the power production is constrained by hydro inflow f_{irt}' and capacity H_r' ,

$$0 \leq h_{rt}' \leq f_{irt}', \quad (12)$$

$$0 \leq h_{rt}' \leq H_r'. \quad (13)$$

Hydro generation is the sum of hydro RoR generation and hydro reservoir generation,

$$h_{rt} = h_{rt}' + f_{ort}'. \quad (14)$$

3.7 Transmission

The trade is upper-bounded by transmission capacity:

$$0 \leq \gamma_{rrt} \leq z_{rrt} \quad (15)$$

The energy in storage is bounded by the maximum energy that can be stored,

$$0 \leq \theta_{rt} \leq u_r; \quad (16)$$

The energy out from storage is bounded by the storage level in the previous time-step,

$$\varepsilon_{rt} \leq \theta_{r,t-1}; \quad (17)$$

The energy into storage is bounded by the space left in the storage,

$$\delta_{rt} \leq u_r - \theta_{rt}; \quad (18)$$

The level in storage is consistent with the charging and discharging in each hour,

$$\theta_{r,t+1} = \theta_{rt} + \eta_s \delta_{rt} - \varepsilon_{rt}, \quad (19)$$

where the constraint is circular so that the storage level in the last time-step of the year equals the storage level for the first time-step of the year.

3.8 Demand-side Resource

The demand-side resource adopted in this implementation is demand-response or price-responsive demand curtailment. In a given time period t , consumers aggregated in segment n can curtail their demand with the marginal value of electricity consumption (variable cost), C_n . The amount of curtailed demand is upper limited by the fraction of demand in segment n , φ_n , times the hourly demand D_{rt} ,

$$v_{nrt} \leq \varphi_n D_{rt}. \quad (20)$$

4. Nodal Net Average System Cost

The total system cost of, for instance, the European electricity system is well defined and can readily be used as indicators to compare different scenarios [4]. However, evaluating the cost of an individual country in the continental electricity system is more difficult. The generation capacity invested in a specific country may end up supplying electricity to neighboring countries. If only the capital and operational costs in each country are assessed, the importing country may be perceived as having a very low-cost electricity system. However, this is not necessarily true as the cost of the imported electricity is ignored. This problem can be avoided if countries are studied in isolation, but this obviously fails to capture the interplay with surrounding regions.

Tranberg et al. [5] introduced a method to assign the shares of capital and operational costs associated with imported electricity from generation capacities abroad to the importing countries through tracing the power flow. Pattupara and Kannan [6] incorporated revenue from electricity trade in the system cost and evaluated the effect of electricity trade on the national electricity system cost. We use a similar approach in this paper by introducing the concept of nodal net average system cost (NNASC) to represent the net electricity system cost for each node in the model. This concept incorporates the system-wide capital and operational costs of generation and transmission, profit of trade (revenue from exporting electricity less the cost of importing electricity), and congestion rent¹.

¹ *Congestion rent* is defined as the price difference times the power flow over a transmission network constraint.

Node r imports and exports electricity at the nodal price λ_{rt} , and receives the congestion rent resulting from electricity export. The capital cost of transmission infrastructures assigned to node r is assumed to be proportional to the share of annual congestion rent it receives. Therefore, the annual nodal net system cost (ANNSC) for node (country or region) r is

$$\begin{aligned}
C_r = & \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{n \in X} (C_n x_{nr} + R_n \alpha_{nrt}) + \sum_{n \in Y} (C_n y_{nr}) + C_s u_r + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{n \in M} (C_n v_{nrt}) + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r' \in R} (\gamma_{r'rt} \lambda_{rt}) \\
& - \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r' \in R} (\gamma_{rr't} \lambda_{rt}) - \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r' \in R} (\gamma_{rr't} (\lambda_{r't} - \lambda_{rt})) \\
& + \sum_{r' \in R} (C_{rr'z_{rr'}} \frac{\sum_{t \in T} \gamma_{rr't} (\lambda_{r't} - \lambda_{rt})}{\sum_{t \in T} \gamma_{rr't} (\lambda_{r't} - \lambda_{rt}) + \sum_{t \in T} \gamma_{r'rt} (\lambda_{rt} - \lambda_{r't})}), \tag{21}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\sum_{t \in T} \sum_{n \in X} (C_n x_{nr} + R_n \alpha_{nrt}) + \sum_{n \in Y} (C_n y_{nr}) + C_s u_r + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{n \in M} (C_n v_{nrt})$ is the overall generation costs in r ; $\sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r' \in R} (\gamma_{r'rt} \lambda_{rt})$ is the cost of electricity import; $\sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r' \in R} (\gamma_{rr't} \lambda_{rt})$ is the revenue from electricity export; $\sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r' \in R} (\gamma_{rr't} (\lambda_{r't} - \lambda_{rt}))$ is the sum of congestion rent that r receives; $C_{rr'z_{rr'}}$ is the investment cost of transmission line rr' ; $\frac{\sum_{t \in T} \gamma_{rr't} (\lambda_{r't} - \lambda_{rt})}{\sum_{t \in T} \gamma_{rr't} (\lambda_{r't} - \lambda_{rt}) + \sum_{t \in T} \gamma_{r'rt} (\lambda_{rt} - \lambda_{r't})}$ is the share of annual congestion rent, resulting from transmission line rr' , allocated to r .

Dividing the ANNSC by the total electricity consumption in node r yields the corresponding nodal net average system cost (NNASC, represented by C_r^{av}). The NNASC manages to capture the net average system cost for an individual country or region in the interconnected electricity system.

$$\begin{aligned}
C_r^{av} = & \left[\sum_{t \in T} \sum_{n \in X} (C_n x_{nr} + R_n \alpha_{nrt}) + \sum_{n \in Y} (C_n y_{nr}) + C_s u_r + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{n \in M} (C_n v_{nrt}) + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r' \in R} (\gamma_{r'rt} \lambda_{rt}) \right. \\
& - \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r' \in R} (\gamma_{rr't} \lambda_{rt}) - \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r' \in R} (\gamma_{rr't} (\lambda_{r't} - \lambda_{rt})) \\
& \left. + \sum_{r' \in R} (C_{rr'z_{rr'}} \frac{\sum_{t \in T} \gamma_{rr't} (\lambda_{r't} - \lambda_{rt})}{\sum_{t \in T} \gamma_{rr't} (\lambda_{r't} - \lambda_{rt}) + \sum_{t \in T} \gamma_{r'rt} (\lambda_{rt} - \lambda_{r't})}) \right] / \sum_{t \in T} D_{rt}. \tag{22}
\end{aligned}$$

5. Software Implementation

The model was implemented in Julia using JuMP [7] and was optimized using the Gurobi solver software [8]. The calculation time is between 12 and 32 minutes depending on the specific scenarios. Dell Precision 5820 Tower with Intel® Core™ i9-9900X CPU @3.50 GHz, RAM 64 GB and Windows 10, 64-bit system, is used for the implementation of the model.

6. Data Resource

The countries included in the model are EU-28 (excluding Cyprus and Malta) plus Switzerland, Norway, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, and Montenegro. The network topology of this model is shown in Fig. 2, where Sweden is divided into 4 regions, Norway is divided into 5 regions, Finland is divided into 2 regions and the rest of Europe is divided into 11 regions. In total there are 22 regions in the model and these regions are interconnected with transmission grids.

Fig. 2. Regions and transmission network used in the case study.

SE: Sweden

NO: Norway

DK: Denmark

Fi: Finland

BNL: Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg

DE: Germany

BAL: Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania

PL: Poland

IR: Ireland

UK: United Kingdom

FR: France, Monaco

CEN: Austria, Switzerland, Czechia, Hungary, Slovakia, Romania, Liechtenstein

SPA: Spain, Portugal, Andorra, Gibraltar

MED: Greece, Bulgaria, Italy, San Marino, Vatican City, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Montenegro, Kosovo, Albania, Macedonia, Malta

6.1 Cost Data

The cost data used to calculate the annualized costs are summarized in Table 1. The parameters are mainly taken from [9].

Table 1: Cost data and technical parameters

Technology	Investment cost [\$/kW]	Variable O&M costs [\$/MWh]	Fixed O&M costs [\$/kW/yr]	Fuel costs [\$/MWh fuel]	Lifetime [years]	Efficiency/ Round-trip efficiency
Natural gas OCGT	460	5	17	35	30	0.4
Natural gas CCGT	920	6	20	35	30	0.6
Biogas OCGT	460	5	17	70	30	0.4
Biogas CCGT	920	6	20	70	30	0.6
Biomass CHP ^a	3500	0	100	50	25	0.25
Nuclear	4700 ^b	0	120	10	60	0.4
Onshore wind	1090 ^c	0	40	n/a	25	n/a
Offshore wind	2880	0	90	n/a	25	n/a
Solar	690	0	30	n/a	25	n/a

Hydro reservoir	2300	0	25	n/a	80	n/a
Hydro RoR	3450	0	70	n/a	80	n/a
Transmission	460 ^d \$/MWkm	0	0	n/a	40	0.95
Batteries	220 ^e \$/kWh	0	0	n/a	10	0.9

- a. IEA ETSAP. [10]
- b. NREL. [11]
- c. Sepulveda et al. [12]
- d. Schlachtberger et al. [4]

6.1 Demand Data

The hourly electricity demand in 2014 is used as the load profile for each country and the data is obtained from ENTSO-E [13]. Demand data for the four regions of Sweden and five regions of Norway are taken from Nord Pool [14]. The demand data of Finland is divided into two regions in accordance with the share of annual electricity consumption in each region [15]. To account for potential electrification of other sectors by 2045, the electricity demand is linearly scaled up by 33% based on the reference scenarios for EU countries [16, 17] for sensitivity analysis.

Appendix 1. Hourly electricity demand of Europe [13]

Appendix 2. Hourly electricity demand of Sweden bidding zones [14]

Appendix 3. Hourly electricity demand of Norway bidding zones [18]

Appendix 4. Annual electricity consumption in each region in Finland [15]

6.2 Nuclear Capacity

New nuclear power can be invested in countries with existing nuclear fleet and the upper limit is the current capacity. Three exceptions are Germany, Switzerland and Belgium, where there are clear policies to phase out nuclear power plants [19, 20]. This means that the maximum potential nuclear energy supply is equivalent to 20% of current European electricity demand if a capacity factor of 80% is applied to nuclear power.

Appendix 5. Net generation capacity of Europe [21]

6.3 Hydro Capacity and Inflow

The capacities of hydro reservoir and hydro run of river (RoR) remain constant at the current level. Therefore, no expansion of hydro is considered due to environmental concerns. The inflow for each country is based on reference [4] and this value is divided into reservoir and RoR inflow which is commensurate with the share of installed hydropower capacity. Some of the capacity data are later

updated according to the data source in ENTSO-E [21] as input to REX model. The minimum environmental flow constraint is set as 5% of the mean annual inflow.

Appendix 6. Hydro reservoir capacity and total hydro energy storage [4]

Appendix 7. Hydro inflow [4]

6.4 Wind and Solar Data

The potential of wind and solar power capacity is calculated based on a GIS model [22]. The assumptions on wind and solar photovoltaic farm densities (W/m^2) and available land are shown in Table 2, where the available land is given in % of land where populated areas, natural parks, lakes, mountains etc. are excluded.

Table 2: Assumptions on capacity limits for wind and solar photovoltaic. The density is the power output per unit area of a typical solar or wind farm.

	Solar Photovoltaic	Wind Onshore	Wind Offshore
Density [W/m^2]	45	5	8
Available land [%]	5%	8%	33%

Appendix 8. Wind data

Appendix 9. Solar data

6.5 Biomass and Biogas Power Plants

Due to resource endowment, the fuel consumption of biogas power plants is upper bounded to 5% of annual electricity demand. The biomass fueled combined heat and power (CHP) plants are invested and the electricity generation follows the current pattern which is coupled with the heat demand.

Appendix 10. Biomass price in Sweden [23]

Appendix 11. CHP capacity and generation of EU28 [24]

Appendix 12. Monthly CHP generation of Sweden [25]

6.6 Transmission

We assume the future international transmission grids are high-voltage direct current (HVDC) connections and use the transport model to represent the electricity trade. The length of the transmission line is set by the distance between the geographical mid-points of each region [4]. The cost of installing converter station is 170 \$/kW [4]. The current transmission capacity is based on the

upper value for net transfer capacities in [26]. Transmission capacity inside Sweden, Norway and Finland are taken from Nordpool [27].

6.7 Demand-side Resource

In this implementation, the demand side resources are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Scenarios of demand-response

Scenarios	No demand-response	5% demand-response (base case)	10% demand-response
Number of segments	0	5	5
Variable cost ^a	0	60-70-80-90-100	60-70-80-90-100
Size of each segment ^b	0	1	2
Total price-responsive demand ^c	0	5	10

a. Variable cost of demand-response in each demand segment as a percentage of the value of lost load (\$1000/MWh)

b. Size of each demand segment as a percentage of hourly demand

c. Total price-responsive demand as a percentage of hourly demand

6.8 Carbon Cap and CO₂ Emission

The CO₂ emission constraint is 10 g/kWh. The emission factor of natural gas is 198 gCO₂/kWh.

7. Input Data

All the input data are included in the file Input data.

8. Results

All the results are included in the file results.

9. Model Codes

All the model codes are included in the file Model codes. One can run the model with JuMP v0.18.6 and Gurobi solver.

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